

The syntheses of benzocondensed furans, benzofuranopyrazoles and benzofuranopyrimidines have been reported⁸. We report here the synthesis of some new benzofuran and pyranobenzofuran derivatives.

Results and Discussion

Thymoxyacetic acid (1) was prepared by the reaction of the thymol with chloroacetic acid in presence of alkali⁴ followed by the cyclisation in presence of polyphosphoric acid to give benzofuranone (2), the formation of which was evidenced by disappearance of acidic OH encountered at δ 14.5 in the pmr spectrum and a broad ir band at 3 100–2 400 cm^{-1} . The conversion of 2 into 3 was confirmed by appearance of the ester carbonyl and furanocarbonyl around 1 740 and 1 720 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum. The formation of the substituted benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-3(1*H*)-one from 3 and substituted arylhydrazide was confirmed by disappearance of the furocarbonyl and ester carbonyl and appearance of the amidocarbonyl at 1 700 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of 4.

The conversion of 2 into 5 was confirmed by the appearance of δ -lactone carbonyl ir bands at 1 755 and 1 720 cm^{-1} due to α, β -unsaturation and encountering of additional signal at δ 2.4 (=C-CH₃) in the pmr spectrum. The coupling of the diazotised substituted anilines with 5 was evidenced by the band at 1 400 cm^{-1} (N=O) in the ir spectrum of 6.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃ or CCl₄) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compound was checked by tlc using silica gel G.

Thymoxyacetic acid was prepared from thymol and chloroacetic acid as a starting material by a known method.

4-Methyl-7-isopropylbenzofuran-3-(2*H*-one) (2): A mixture of thymoxyacetic acid (0.033 mol) in polyphosphoric acid (15 ml) and P₂O₅ (5 g) was stirred for 30 min and heated gently on a water-bath at 70° for about 2 h, then cooled and poured in an ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and recrystallised from alcohol, (4.1 g, 61.7%), m p. 114° (Found: C, 75.70; H, 7.30. C₁₃H₁₄O₂ requires: C, 75.78; H, 7.36%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 720 (cyclic C=O), 1 600 (C=C) and 1 035–1 050 cm^{-1} (–O–); δ CDCl₃ 1.1 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.2 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH₂CO), 6.8–6.9 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C₆-ArH) and 7.0–7.2 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C₅-ArH).

4-Methyl-7-isopropyl-2,3-dihydro-3-oxo-benzofuran-2-ethylcarboxylate (3): To a mixture of 2 (0.025 mol) and ethylchloroformate (0.05 mol) in acetone (40 ml), K₂CO₃ (5 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting

Synthesis of some New Benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and Pyrano[3,2-*b*]benzofurans

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A number of investigations have reported the antifungal and antibacterial activities of the benzofuran derivatives¹. The esterogenic activity of some furocoumarins has been extensively recorded².

solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, (40 g, 61.2%), m.p. 88° (Found: C, 68.5; H, 6.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires: C, 68.70; H, 6.8%; ν_{max} (KBr) 1740 (ester C=O), 1720 (cyclic C=O), 1580–1600 (C=C) and 1035–1060 cm^{-1} (–O–); δ (CDCl₃) 1.1 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.3 (3H, t, CH₂ ester), 2.3 (3H, s, C₄-ArCH₃), 3.2 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH₂ ester), 4.6 (1H, s, O-CH) and 6.8–6.9 (1H, s, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-C₆-H).

2-Aroyl-6-isopropyl-8-methylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyrazol-3 (1 H)-one (4): To a solution of 3 (0.00125 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), *p*-methoxybenzhydrazide (0.00125 mol) was added and the mixture refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath and then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol to furnish 4a (0.33 g, 73.9%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 69.10; H, 5.30; N, 7.5. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires: C, 69.20; H, 5.40; N, 7.60%; ν_{max} (KBr) 3300–3250 (NH) 1690–1700br (CON) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 1.1 (6H, d, $2 \times CH_3$), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.2 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 6.8–7.3 (6H, m, ArH).

6-Isopropyl-9-methylpyrano[3,2-b benzofuran- (22H)-one (5): A mixture of compound 3 (0.03 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.03 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (20 ml) was refluxed for ~ 7 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting gummy solid was recrystallised from methanol, (4.53 g, 59.0%), m.p. 108° (Found: C, 74.75; H, 6.10. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires: C, 75.0; H, 6.25%; ν_{max} (KBr) 1755 and 1730 (α,β -unsaturated δ -lactone C=O), 1580 (C=C) and 1050 cm^{-1} (–O–); δ (CDCl₃) 1.1 (6H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, $2 \times CH_3$), (3H, s, C₉-ArCH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, C₃-CH₃), 3.2 (1H, m, CH), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH), 6.8–6.9 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-C₈-H) and 7.0–7.1 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C₇-H).

3-Phenyldiazo-4,9-dimethyl-6-isopropylpyrano [3, 2-b) benzofuran-2 (1 H)-one (6): To a solution of 5 (0.001 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), a diazotised solution of aniline (0.002 mol) and CH₃COONa (1.6 g) were added at 0° and kept overnight. The separated solid was filtered and extracted with chloroform. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure furnished brown coloured solid which was further recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 6f (0.185 g, 51.3%), m.p. 106° (Found: C, 72.20; H, 5.50; N, 7.70. $C_{22}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires: C, 72.10; H, 5.55; N, 7.77 %); ν_{max} (KBr) 1755 and 1735 (α,β -unsaturated δ lactone C=O), 1600 (C=C), 1400 (N=N), 1060 (–O–); δ (CDCl₃) 1.1 (3H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, $2 \times CH_3$), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, C₃-CH₃) and 6.8–7.3 (7H, m, ArH).

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TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF SOME COMPOUNDS 4 AND 6.

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
4a	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃	120	71	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂
4b	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -Cl	110	61	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl
4c	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	225	67	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂
4d	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂	180	63	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃
4e	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₅ -OCH ₂ -CH ₃	84	58	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂
6f	C ₆ H ₅	106	61	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂
6g	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂	99	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃
6h	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂	90	64	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃
6i	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂	124	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃
6j	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -Cl	85	69	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl
6k	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃	110	75	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂
6l	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃	95	80	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂

* All compounds were analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N.